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REPORT ON PROFICIENCY TEST FOR THE HARMONIZATION OF DETECTION OF EM/EG IN COMPLEX SAMPLES: SEQUENCING USING RSE AND NGS (MEME WP4-T3)

INDEX

1. Aims	2
2. Background and principle of the methods	2
2.1 <i>Targeted</i> Whole Genome Amplification with Nanopore sequencing	2
2.2 Metabarcoding and Illumina sequencing	3
3. Material	3
4. Results	4
5. Discussion and conclusion	5
6. References	6

This proficiency test was conducted as part of the activities of MEME (Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus* s.l. in Europe: development and harmonisation of diagnostic methods in the food chain), a Joint Research Project under One Health EJP.

1. Aims

The general aim of this proficiency test was to contribute to evaluation of the potential of sequencing methods developed towards Region Specific Extraction (RSE) with long-read sequencing (MEME task WP3-T3) and metabarcoding Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *E. granulosus* s.l. (Eg) in complex samples, such as faecal samples.

The work focused on two aims:

Aim 1) to determine whether the platforms were able to detect DNA from Em and Eg parasites

and **Aim 2)** testing DNA extracted from spiked faecal samples.

2. Background and principle of the methods

Detection of Em and Eg from complex samples (faeces) can be useful for epidemiological studies of prevalence in definitive hosts.

The scope of this proficiency test was limited to NGS methods that are in development, or implemented in MEME consortium partner laboratories, for detection of Em and Eg, in particular in complex samples. Two MEME partner laboratories had such methods in development or established: targeted Whole Genome Amplification (WGA) followed by Nanopore sequencing (NVI), and 18S rRNA metabarcoding using Illumina sequencing (SSI).

A new method for mitogenome sequencing of RSE samples with Illumina NGS technology (FLI) was not available at the time of this PT activity.

2.1 Targeted Whole Genome Amplification with Nanopore sequencing

For the purpose of identification of Em and Eg in complex samples generated from region specific DNA extraction (RSE), a protocol under development for long-read sequencing (Oxford Nanopore Sequencing) was available from Task WP3-T3. This task aimed to explore nanopore sequencing of templates containing low amounts of parasite material prepared from magnetic capture DNA extraction. Identification was carried out on assembled sequences that was generated from DNA samples.

2.2 Metabarcoding and Illumina sequencing

DNA was amplified as previously described (Krogsgaard et al 2018; Ring et al 2017) using 3 primer sets (G3F1/G3R1, G4F3/G4R3, and G6F1/G6R1) targeting the hypervariable regions V3-V4 (G3 and G6 primers) and V3–V5 (G4) of the 18S rDNA gene. The library was prepared by an amplification PCR and an adaptor PCR as described by Ring et al. (2017). The complete bioinformatic pipeline, BION, based on raw sequence data was used for the analysis of the amplicons (Ring et al, 2017).

3. Material

For **Aim 1**, the laboratories tested DNA provided by the European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites (EURLP) as part of the proficiency test program for the molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. in 2022. The test panel consisted of prepared DNA from *E. multilocularis*, *E. granulosus* s.s., and *Taenia saginata*. The laboratories had participated in the EURLP proficiency test and were aware of the correct results, and thus they were not blinded for this proficiency test. Testing was conducted in 2022. DNA from these EURLP samples did not contain faecal material, and had been prepared from parasite material (adult worms or metacestodes) with the DNeasy Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen). The DNA samples were stored frozen at -20 degrees Celsius until testing with these new methods.

In order to address **Aim 2**, attempts were made to assess if RSE-extracted material by the

method of Isaksson et al. (2014) was possible to identify using this Oxford Nanopore Technologies long-read sequence platform. Samples were treated as per the manual method of Isaksson et al. (2014), or with various modifications of this. For more details see WP3-T3.

For the metabarcoding platform, pooled fox faeces (3 gram per sample), already tested negative for Em were used as matrix for testing the method's ability to detect and identify Em in complex samples. The samples (4) were spiked with 1, 5, and 10 eggs as well as 1 worm. Additionally a negative control containing only faeces was included. DNA was extracted according to Maksimov et al (2019). Briefly, each sample was mixed with 400 µl 0.5 mm zirconium oxide beads and 200 µl 2 mm zirconium oxide beads (MP Biomedicals) in addition to 9 ml homogenization and lysis buffer and 3 ml of 5M NaCl in a 15 ml tube (Sarstedt). The samples were bead-beaten using a FastPrep homogenizer (MP Bio, Santa Ana CA, USA). The bead-beating was followed by centrifugation. The supernatant was then recovered and 200 µl was used as input for the QIAmp DNA stool mini kit (Qiagen, Aarhus, Denmark). From this point, DNA extraction was performed following manufacturer's guidelines. The spiked samples were confirmed positive for Em DNA by qPCR.

4. Results

For **Aim 1**) All three EURLP-samples were correctly detected and annotated to the correct species using both NGS approaches.

For **Aim 1**), nanopore sequencing produced several good coverage regions spanning different areas of the mtDNA, of high quality parasite samples prepared with standard DNA isolation. The sequence data from these samples allowed several separate mtDNA regions from that parasite to be used for successful identification. The samples prepared with RSE proved to be a lot more challenging hence **Aim 2**) for this platform failed.

For **Aim 2**) Illumina sequencing followed by data analysis using BION, were not able to

detect Em DNA.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The nanopore sequencing approach targeting mtDNA, can be useful as an identification tool, when performed on high quality parasite samples, and the current results show that it can successfully identify all EURL samples that were tested. This approach allows a substantial amount of mtDNA data to be generated from a single sample, significantly more than what is available through Sanger-sequencing approaches, in a comparable time-frame. The multiple several hundreds, to thousands, of nucleotides uncovered make up a valuable sequence data-set for a sample that allow it to be identified, or sequence data that can be used for phylogenetic analyses. Results show however, that for complex samples subjected to RSE, the current protocol does not allow consistent successful identification, warranting more development work for this category of samples.

The results support that the metabarcoding platform on the Illumina platform currently running at SSI is suitable to detect and correctly identify *E. multilocularis*, *E. granulosus s.s.*, and *T. saginata* in high quality parasite samples. In regard to complex samples, further tests are needed to evaluate how well the method will detect a broader panel of *Echinococcus* spp. including the *E. granulosus s.l.* complex. The missed detection of Em in complex samples (Aim 2) may be due to the potential low amount of DNA present in the 200 µl supernatant used of the approximately 8 ml produced by the pre-extraction treatment. Further analyses are needed as other DNA extraction protocols may be more suited for a metabarcoding pipeline using 18S rRNA primers. However, the results suggest that metabarcoding may be a useful tool for the screening of *Echinococcus* spp.

6. References

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